

A TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR EXAMINING THE TUTOR PERFORMANCE, STUDY MATERIALS, LEARNING METHODS, MANAGEMENT OF LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND STUDENTS' LEARNING MOTIVATION

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Abstract

The research aims to examine the relationships between tutor performance, learning materials, learning methods, and management of the learning environment regarding learning motivation at the Community Learning Center. The study group consisted of 72 students who received non-formal education. The data were collected via an andragogical questionnaire. The relationships between the study variables were analyzed via correlational analysis and regression analysis. The correlation analysis revealed that the correlation/relationship between tutor performance (X1), learning materials (X2), learning methods (X3), and management of the learning environment (X4) on learning motivation (Y) could be said to be significant where the r count is 0.613 with a sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Effectively, the tutor's performance, learning materials, learning methods, and management of the learning environment influence or contribute 37.5% to learning motivation, whereas other factors outside the research variables influence the remaining 62.5%. It was found that the variables that contributed most to learning motivation were learning methods, learning materials, management of the learning environment, and tutor performance.

Keywords: Tutor Performance, Learning Materials, Learning Methods, Learning Environment Management, Learning Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The Community Learning Center, also known as the *Pusat Kegiatan Belajar Masyarakat (PKBM)*, is a non-formal education unit that houses many different types of non-formal education programs (Adiatmana & Fatimah, 2022). These types of education include functional literacy, Package a pursuit, Package B pursuit, and Package C pursuit, as well as courses and other types of education (Utami & Suyatmi, 2017). In general, community members act as PKBM managers and organizers; however, the government (specifically, the Ministry of National Education, operating via the non-formal education or *Pendidikan Luar Sekolah (PLS)* program at the provincial, district, or municipal level) provides facilitation.

The effectiveness of the education program that PKBM organizes depends on how the results (output) and impact (outcomes) are referred to as non-formal education goals on the object of the education program, also known as learning citizens (Rahabav & Souisa, 2021). This purpose is functionally integrated with other subsystems of non-formal education, including the components (input from facilities, raw input, environmental input, and other inputs) and processes (Sardimi et al., 2022).

Suppose this is related to tutors' learning processes in non-formal education programs (Arslan et al., 2019). In that case, the mentoring process can increase the learning

motivation of the learning community to carry out the learning process effectively by forming a mentoring process to increase the learning motivation of the learning community by implementing adult education theories. In other words, if this is related to the learning process in non-formal education programs carried out by tutors, then the mentoring process can be sought, known as andragogy (Díaz-Pinzón, 2019; Hasibuan et al., 2022).

A tutor has to be able to and have a strong willingness to carry out his efforts in attaining the goals of the non-formal education program organized by the PKBM (Rosadi & Herawan, 2021). Additionally, a tutor needs to be able to overcome any challenges experienced by the PKBM and the tutor himself. Students are the end goal of implementing non-formal education initiatives (Blândul, 2021). In the process of putting the program into action, one of the aspects that will be included in the teaching and learning procedure will take place in the form of tutorials, which will be conducted face-to-face between tutors and students (Singh et al., 2022). In addition, there will be opportunities for independent learning, which will require the participation of the students. This indicates that there has to be a strong willingness among the learning community members to participate in learning activities consistently. The teaching and learning process can only function well if citizens are willing to learn. In contrast to the tutor, learning may continue even in the absence of a tutor (Díaz & Cano, 2019; Siregar, 2021). This is because the citizen who learns is the target of this learning.

According to the observations that have been made, several issues have the potential to impede the smooth operation of the education program, particularly in the equality education program (Aytaç, 2021). These issues include a need for seriousness in the implementation of learning and a frequent disregard for what is instructed by tutors (Lestiyawati, 2020). On the one hand, the tutor wants to carry out the learning process regularly and even has to carry out learning activities more often, but on the other hand, the tutor himself is hampered by the lack of presence of the learning community, which reduces the portion of meetings with the students and the enthusiasm of the tutor himself. The tutor wants to carry out the learning process regularly and has to carry out learning activities more often (Admiraal et al., 2021). The absence of regular attendance by locals interested in learning is the issue that creates the most significant friction for PKBM (Apandi & Wasliman, 2022). Even though the resident students have been provided with theory by the tutor, certain students need help comprehending and comprehending the equality learning content.

There needs to be more motivation among the residents who are learning, which leads to their tendency to ignore the learning process (Rahma et al., 2019; Hazizah et al., 2024). As a result, there is also a need for more enthusiasm among the residents who are learning, leading to a tendency on their part to participate in the learning process rarely. Because the learning community will tend to lack respect for what is communicated by the tutor or educator if the degree of motivation that the tutor offers tends to be poor or does not make the learning community interested in what is being conveyed,

It is crucial to develop the right circumstances for residents learning in the package C program in order to overcome all of this (Elihami & Ibrahim, 2019; Nengsih et al., 2024). Specifically, during the learning process, tutors play a key role in enhancing the motivation and accomplishment of Students in the learning process because there is a very low likelihood of being able to boost the accomplishment of people who are

studying the package C program if the degree of inspiration offered by the boring teacher is extremely low. The tutor must be able to be the originator of new ideas and innovate new ones. The tutor must be one of the most powerful factors in the learning process (Hang & Van, 2020; Hiltrimartin et al., 2024). Given the information presented here, it is essential to understand the teaching strategies used by instructors.

Based on the information presented above on the difficulties, the following may be determined: 1. The environment in PKBM has a low level of motivation, which means that the residents who are studying tend to neglect the teachings that the tutor is teaching. The unappealing instructional practices and resources are to blame for the inhabitants' lack of interest in attending school and participating in their educational opportunities. Inability to effectively manage the setting in which topics are being learned. On the other hand, it has yet to be shown that any of these issues are connected. Because of this, it is of the utmost importance that an investigation using the scientific method be carried out to demonstrate that all of the factors are connected. This research attempts to investigate the links between the tutor's performance, learning materials, techniques, and the management of the learning environment as they pertain to learning motivation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is a quantitative method that was carried out, and it was conducted using correlational survey techniques (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019). Within the context of this paradigm, the purpose of this study is to evaluate the degree to which learning motivation is affected by the instructor's effectiveness, the study materials, the learning techniques, and the management of the learning environment. Seventy-two PKBM students were a part of the study sample that was taken. The information was acquired outside of regular school hours after receiving permission from the administration at each institution involved. Each participant's right to privacy was protected, and they were given a rundown of the resources at their disposal. The original version of the scale was developed by Putri (2015), and then it was adjusted to be used in the current study. The scale generates an overall score, and each component receives a Likert scale from one to five points. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyse the study's outcomes (Seeram, 2019). In addition, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine whether the independent variables statistically predicted the dependent variable (Montgomery et al., 2021). This was done in order to determine whether or not the independent factors statistically predicted the dependent variable.

RESULTS

The relationships between the dependent variable (i.e., Learning Motivation) and independent variables (i.e., Tutor Performance, Study Materials, Learning Methods, and Learning Environment Management) were measured with correlation analysis. The results are presented below in Table 1.

Table 1: Correlation analysis results

Variables	Tutor Performance (X1)	Learning Materials (X2)	Learning Method (X3)	Learning Environment Management (X4)	Learning Motivation (Y)
Tutor Performance (X1)	1	.711	.795	.828	.447
Learning Materials (X2)	.711	1	.748	.822	.558
Learning Method (X3)	.795	.748	1	.828	.571
Learning Environment Management (X4)	.828	.822	.828	1	.487
Learning Motivation (Y)	.447	.558	.571	.487	1

These are the conclusions reached after doing a correlation study. There is a significant relationship between these two variables since the observed correlation between them is 0.447, and the significance level between them is $0.000 < 0.05$. As a result, with an r-count of 0.558 and a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, we can conclude that X2 and Y are strongly connected. The following discovery is a significant relationship or correlation between X3 and Y ($r = 0.571$, Sig. = $0.000 < 0.05$). After that, one may conclude that there is a significant connection between the two variables since the estimated r-count for the correlation between X4 and Y is 0.487, and the significance threshold for this correlation is $0.000 < 0.05$.

Table 2: Summary of simple correlation and multiple correlation results

No	Correlation	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Coefficient of Determination (r ²)	Sig.
1	Ry ₁	0.447	0.200	0,000
2	Ry ₂	0.558	0.311	0,000
3	Ry ₃	0.571	0.326	0,000
4	Ry ₄	0.487	0.237	0,000
5	Ry ₁₂₃₄	0,613	0.375	0,000

When the r-count is 0.447, and the sig-value is $0.000 < 0.05$, one may infer a substantial correlation or connection between Tutor Performance (X1) and Learning Motivation. This may be inferred from the fact that there is a significant association between the two variables. At this juncture, it is reasonable to come to this judgment about the situation (Y). The degree of statistical significance for the association between study aids (X2) and interest in learning (Y) is 0.000 ($r = 0.558$; Sig = 0.000). This indicates that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. This result remains unchanged at the threshold of significance known as $0.000 < 0.05$. Next, the r-count of 0.571 and the Sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$ imply that there is a correlation between Learning Method (X3) and Learning Motivation that is statistically significant. This conclusion may be drawn from the fact that there is a positive relationship between the two variables (Y). After that, while considering the r-count of 0.487 and the sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$, one can conclude that there is a substantial correlation or relationship between Learning Environment Management (X4) and Learning Motivation (Y).

Table 3: Summary of results of relative contribution and effective contribution

No	Independent Variable	Relative Contribution	Effective Contribution
1	Tutor Performance (X1)	18.6%	6.97%
2	Learning Materials (X2)	29.0%	10.87%
3	Learning Method (X3)	30.3%	11.38%
4	Learning Environment Management (X4)	22.1%	8.28%
Total		100%	37.5%

The level of learner motivation (Y) is determined by Y, and the performance of the tutor has a large relative effect on that level (18.6%). (X1). A significant contributor of 6.97% of the total is also listed. Then, the effective impact or contribution of the Learning Materials variable (X2) to the Learning Motivation (Y) variable is 10.87%, but its relative contribution of 29% is very significant since it is much higher. This suggests that the variable representing Learning Materials significantly impacts the learner's desire to learn. The subsequent variable, Learning Method (X3), has a significant effect or contribution on Learning Motivation (Y), with a margin of 30.3%; however, in practice, it only has an influence or contribution of 11.38 per cent on Learning Motivation. After that, the impact or contribution of effective learning environment management on learning motivation (Y) is 8.28%, whereas the relative importance of the learning environment management variable (X4) on learning motivation (Y) is 22.1%. This is because effective learning environment management positively impacts learning motivation (Y). This is because efficient management of the learning environment has a beneficial influence on the desire to study (Y).

There is a statistically significant relationship between the overall impact of teacher performance (X1), learning materials (X2), learning approaches (X3), and management of the learning environment (X4) on learning motivation (Y). The r count is 0.613, and the Sig value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Learning motivation is effectively impacted or contributed to by the performance of the tutor, learning materials, learning techniques, and management of the learning environment to the tune of 37.5%, with the remaining 62.5% of learning motivation being influenced by factors that are outside the scope of the study variables. Consequently, it was found that the teaching methods were the most significant element in promoting students' interest in learning, followed by the subject matter of the courses, the classroom administration, and the quality of the instruction provided by the teachers.

DISCUSSION

As a result of the research, the quality of the tutor, the study materials, and the management of the learning environment were the factors that best predicted learning motivation. In addition, the regression model demonstrated that the overlap between these factors was a significant factor in adequately explaining learning motivation. In light of this context, the findings of this study highlight the significance of independent variables such as tutor performance (d'Arripe-Longueville et al., 2002; Chikileva, 2019; Hattum-Janssen & Vasconcelos, 2008; Pinto et al., 2001), study materials (Lestari, 2020; Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019), the management of the learning environment (Law et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2021) which are effectively enhance motivation for students to study at the PKBM.

First and foremost, the tutor's role in generating learning motivation should be commended (Febriani et al., 2021). Beginning with the role of the tutor as a facilitator, organizer, motivator, director/director, facilitator, evaluator, giving praise, and giving punishment, some roles have not been implemented optimally, specifically the role of the evaluator and giving praise, which tends to be less than optimal (Noviawati & Masjidah, 2020; Sulistiani et al., 2021).

One of the most critical times in learning motivation is the one that encompasses students. This is because there is a propensity for learning to motivate people to attempt new things, which may increase the likelihood of engaging in non-formal

education. Engaging in such non-formal education might put students potentially life-low motivation (Fitria & Irmawita, 2020). Given that students spend most of their time with their friends and relatives, good or bad experiences involving these two groups might have a role in either encouraging or discouraging students to gain motivation (Nazir, 2019). In a similar vein, Frutos et al. (2019) and Oktavia and Jalius (2022) assert that the inner social circle, which includes close friends and family members, is intimately connected to the impulses for learning motivation.

Consequently, students' feelings when in the class may be a crucial determining factor for learning motivation. This was also clear as a consequence of the findings of this research. To be more specific, it implies that persons who want sensation need to be viewed in light of whatever it is that they have been through in the past and are now enduring. If a person originates from a toxic environment and has a history of unpleasant experiences, this person may have a greater propensity to engage in the classroom. On the other side, being surrounded by happy experiences and a supportive environment may decrease the propensity to engage in the classroom. Fitria and Irmawita (2020) discovered a considerable correlation between the quality of the learning environment and the level of motivation in the learning community, and the environment could be more favourable to learning for the training participants. To enrol in classes at PKBM Surya in Padang City to study embroidery. They suggested that PKBM Surya schools create an inviting atmosphere for their embroidery classes so that students would be more inclined to participate in the program.

Study Materials techniques are another idea that might be associated with students' learning motivation (Hardiyanto & Robandi, 2021; Susanti et al., 2022). The individuals' methods of Learning Environment Management may be a factor in the detrimental effects that learning motivation has on an individual's interest in the material teaching. Preparation for teaching is an absolute thing that must be done every time they are going to carry out learning (Guacas & Casal, 2019). The preparation referred to is not only in the form of teaching materials and learning steps that will be carried out but physical and mental preparation to become a donor of knowledge and skills to students (Rudini & Saputra, 2022). According to Tohani (2021), the learning process had certain advantages, including the fact that it was more dynamic and the fact that there was a shift in students' positive behaviour in line with the anticipated learning goals. For this reason, it is essential that new project-based learning be created and implemented in other non-formal education courses, together with the availability of partnerships and practical support for resources.

Moreover, the following part is the relationship between effective learning management and the desire to continue one's education. Using a SWOT analysis, Puspito et al. (2021) identified two techniques for producing graduates: promoting socialization and fostering villages. Evaluating and supervising a plan, entails looking at its foundation, contrasting it with the actual outcomes, and then making adjustments via monitoring, meetings, and reporting (Al Falah, 2019; Párraga et al., 2022). The findings of his investigation suggest that the tutor's learning creativity at PKBM Al Suroya has excellent talents. Tutors who are innovative in learning will boost the learning motivation of the learning community. Then, the variables that impact tutors' learning inventiveness in raising students' learning motivation at PKBM Al Suroya Metro City are the complete support of many parties, both from management, government and even the surrounding environment. However, the tutor's regular tasks and inadequate facilities and infrastructure will also hamper the tutor's inventiveness.

Therefore, the ability to manage a successful learning program will considerably impact the degree of student motivation in a PKBM.

The learning motivation of residents will only rise if the tutor can explore his talents while they are studying, and this will prevent the learning motivation of residents from increasing (Indrawati, 2019; Wahyuni, 2020). Students will be overwhelmed with tutoring that has a tedious tendency to be repetitive. When they first started the learning process at PKBM, the inhabitants felt inferior, insecure, and other emotions along those lines (Triyono, 2019). Therefore, tutors must be able to boost the learning motivation of the residents under their care.

The role of the mentor or instructor in the education process is essential to every activity (Chikileva, 2019; Pinto et al., 2001; Rosadi et al., 2021). If a tutor is willing to act not only as a teacher and mentor but also as a friend, the learning process will go smoothly and successfully (Febriari et al., 2021; Noviawati & Masjidah, 2020; Sulistiani et al., 2021). In the process of learning itself, a tutor needs to be able to select a method that is appropriate to the learning material. In addition, he needs to be able to select the media used by the learning objectives, approaches, and techniques, and he needs to make a lesson plan in the form of learning units (Hardiyanto & Robandi, 2021). Because of this, a tutor has to be creative and have the ability to bring up new thoughts or topics in the learning process so that it becomes more varied for the learning community.

Learning should, first and foremost, be enjoyable, with the end goal of producing a learning community that is highly motivated to continue its education (Sardimi et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2022). Learning has no age restrictions and may occur in any environment (Fitria & Irmawita, 2020). Education should be pursued until the end of one's life. In the end, education should be able to produce human beings who are genuine, informed, conscientious, clever, industrious, honest, fair, ethical, self-disciplined, tolerant, and capable of preserving harmony on both an individual and a societal level (Nazir, 2019; Waty et al., 2023; Putri et al., 2024). As a result, all PKBM institutions are obligated to have the capacity to enhance the level of education they provide, naturally, in a manner that is congruent with the circumstances of the students and the institutions themselves.

When instructors at PKBM are more innovative in the learning process, the motivation of the learning community at PKBM has improved (Lestari, 2020; Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019; Oktavia & Jalius, 2022). When instructors are doing new things, residents who are learning tend to become more enthused. As a result, there has been an increase in the learning motivation of the learning community, which may be attributed to the inventiveness of the tutor's learning. Managing the Learning Environment, as well as the Study Materials and Learning Methods

Students who are adults and are learning are seen to be better prepared than residents who are children and are learning. However, almost everyone has trouble comprehending some concepts (Adiatmana & Fatimah, 2022; Apandi & Wasliman, 2022; Utami & Suyatmi, 2017). Therefore, attentiveness and active dialogue between Students and instructors might boost learning motivation.

Implementing the andragogy learning technique affects the level of ease and comfort experienced by residents of the learning community due to the information being presented to them by tutors and tutors (Farizal, 2020). However, the strategy the tutor takes in getting to know the students and understanding their learning issues will be

significant if the tutor hopes to boost the students' motivation to study, which will affect their growth in learning accomplishment. In addition, it is preferable to assist students in learning to comprehend learning material for tutors or for tutors to deliver learning suited to real-world scenarios or contemporary challenges.

CONCLUSION

This study indicated that instructor quality, study materials, and learning environment management best predicted learning motivation. The tutor's job of motivating students is commendable, but it could have been better executed. Learning motivation is strongly influenced by a student's inner social group and how they feel in class. Students' motivation depends on the learning community's quality and motivation. The setting could be more conducive to learning for training participants. Hence, PKBM Surya schools should make stitching lessons appealing. Teachers must prepare every time they educate, and it is suggested that they boost socializing and build communities to produce graduates. Evaluating and overseeing a strategy involves comparing its basis to the results and making revisions via monitoring, meetings, and reporting. The analysis suggests PKBM. Al Suroya tutor's learning creativity is outstanding. However, the tutor's daily chores and poor infrastructure will limit their creativity. The instructor must be innovative and able to provide fresh ideas and subjects to keep the learning community engaged. Every activity requires a mentor or teacher. To create a highly motivated learning group, learning should be fun. PKBM institutions must improve education for students and meet institutional needs. Andragogy influences residents' comfort and attention, and active discussion between students and instructors may motivate learning.

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